

ReCiPSS

D 8.3-Dissemination Report

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Draft

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1. Introduction

This report follows the completion of dissemination activities carried out by members of the ReCiPSS consortium throughout the duration of the ReCiPSS project, to share project outcomes, and to demonstrate the usefulness of the ReCiPSS results. It lists the dissemination activities carried out during the course of this project and reports any deviations from the “Deliverable 8.2 Dissemination Plan” that was revised in Nov 2018.

The ReCiPSS project consists of a diverse consortium of 13 partners which is represented by 4 research and 9 industrial partners. The industrial partners are represented by Original Equipment Manufacturers (OEMs), technology providers, and knowledge providers. ReCiPSS communication team consists of researchers, professional communicators and graphic designers to ensure that all aspects of the dissemination and communication are covered. KTH is primarily responsible for all project-level dissemination activities. In addition, ReCiPSS partners have their own communication responsible to support the communication team. The graphic design team is provided by SIVCO, which is also supporting the project-level dissemination activities.

The project partners have taken a variety of opportunities to leverage its combined networks of manufacturing, technology, design, academic and circular economy audiences to reach a broad group of stakeholders that could benefit from the ReCiPSS outcomes. Stakeholders targeted by ReCiPSS for dissemination include OEMs, remanufacturers, suppliers, workshops, wholesalers, core brokers, spare parts traders, software community, academic community, designers, manufacturing associations, remanufacturing associations, circular economy associations, circular economy businesses, and policymakers. The ReCiPSS dissemination plan was designed to disseminate the project results and the development of an ecosystem around the project effectively and systematically, in order to guarantee its sustainable impact. The dissemination plan set out the activities during the course of the project that helped communicate the project progress and results. In addition, the wider benefits of circular manufacturing systems were made available publicly online, e.g. through industry events, scientific publications and industrial case studies.

2. Overview of project level communication and dissemination activities

2.1. Graphic identity

Completed activities

To standardise all communication around the project and create a brand identity recognisable to ReCiPSS, a graphic identity has been created and used during the project. This includes a logo and colour palette.

The ReCiPSS logo (see Figure 1) is used in all communications together with the European Commission logo.

The ReCiPSS logo features the text 'ReCiPSS' in a sans-serif font. The 'i' is lowercase and green, while the other letters are dark grey. A green circular arrow icon is positioned above the 'i'.

Figure 1: ReCiPSS logo.

The diagram in Figure 2 shows the overarching material flow of circular manufacturing systems (i.e. raw materials, design, production/remanufacturing, distribution, Consumption/use-reuse-repair, collection recycling).

Figure 2: Overarching material flow of circular manufacturing systems.

The work structure implemented in ReCiPSS to achieve the project goals is shown in Figure 3. It also represents the standardize colour schemes that are used throughout the project communication.

Figure 3: The work structure implemented in ReCiPSS.

Deviations from D8.2 Dissemination Plan

None

2.2. Standardised materials

Completed activities

Distribution materials such as a standard leaflet, press release, and standard overview presentation etc. have been made available to all partners through Projectplace¹ platform. The leaflet presents the key information about the project including aims, approach, reference to the industrial demonstrators and key contact details. Standardised templates have been created for word and PowerPoint documents to standardise project reports. These include the ReCiPSS and EU logos and the ReCiPSS diagram. A branding guide has been created for using the templates that give guidance for font use, references, titles, and image placement.

Deviations from D8.2 Dissemination Plan

None

¹ ProjectPlace is a project management platform used by the ReCiPSS consortium for information and data sharing as well as communication.

2.3. Website

Completed activities

ReCiPSS website was launched in August 2018 and can be accessed at www.recipss.eu. The website is the main dissemination platform, which is a living site. The website provides the central hub of activity for the ReCiPSS project. The website URL has been used in a variety of external communications to share information about the project, including in newsletters and social media posts and is available in English. ReCiPSS partners KTH and SIM are jointly responsible for keeping the website updated and maintaining an editorial role over the content. The website has played the role of the project logbook, which includes information such as project overview, partner information and contacts, advisory board members, public deliverables, publications and news. The website also includes videos of interviews with key ReCiPSS partners answering different questions about the ReCiPSS project. To reach out to a greater audience each partner has published the link to the ReCiPSS website on the website and official social media pages of their organization. The table below shows different categories of posts/publications and their numbers on the ReCiPSS website.

Table 1 Categories of posts

Post category	Number of posts
Number of active pages	35
Scientific publications	27
Public deliverables (until month 52)	21
Posters	5
Flyers	2
Project summary report	2
White paper	1
News / Press release	50+
Events	17

Deviations from D8.2 Dissemination Plan

None

2.4. Industrial case studies

Completed activities

Two demonstrators in ReCiPSS are treated as two case studies in two diverse industrial sectors, i.e. automotive and white goods sectors. The case studies form key content to share with stakeholders and are highlighted throughout all dissemination activities to demonstrate the applicability of the ReCiPSS ideas and results in other industrial sectors. To engage different audiences, the case studies have been presented in a number of formats, as described below.

- Online written case studies: case studies for each of the demonstrators have been embedded in the ReCiPSS website. Updated case studies will be shared in the final project newsletter.
- Video clips: video content is available on the ReCiPSS website and on the ReCiPSS social media pages. This is in the form of the ReCiPSS animation, and short interview clips with key ReCiPSS partners. Different elements of the case studies are discussed in these video clips including the overview of the ReCiPSS project, the industrial demonstrators and the economic and environmental impacts that the project is expected to make
- Educational materials: the two case studies also form the basis of educational material and the consortium's network of universities uses them within relevant courses. For example, the two case studies are taught as part of the master's course on [Circular Manufacturing Systems](#) and PhD course in [Circular Economy and Industrial Systems](#) at KTH Royal Institute of Technology.

Deviations from D8.2 Dissemination Plan

None

2.5. Social media content

Completed activities

ReCiPSS has exploited social media extensively. Dedicated pages were created on LinkedIn, Twitter, and ResearchGate to target, industry, policy and academic audiences. The ReCiPSS LinkedIn page can be accessed through, <https://www.linkedin.com/company/eu-project-ecipss/>. A Twitter handle for the ReCiPSS project can be accessed at the following link: <https://twitter.com/ecipss>. ResearchGate targets academics and can be accessed through <https://www.researchgate.net/project/EU-Project-ReCiPSS>. KTH was primarily responsible to communicate project updates through these channels. In addition, each consortium member used their personal webpage, newsletters, and social media accounts to share information about ReCiPSS including sharing the posts that were put on the ReCiPSS social media pages.

Table 2 Summary of the ReCiPSS social media activities

Platform	Activity/posts	Reach
LinkedIn	More than 50 public posts	316 Followers
Twitter	150+ Tweets	118 Following 113 Followers
ResearchGate	More than 40 publications including deliverables	59 Collaborators

Deviations from D8.2 Dissemination Plan

None

2.6. Public deliverables

Completed activities

A ReCiPSS project community is created on [Zenodo](https://zenodo.org), which collects data and public deliverables. All ReCiPSS public deliverables are published on this platform and on the ReCiPSS website to ensure a high level of dissemination. The guidelines for publishing results of the ReCiPSS project are summarized in Deliverable 8.5 “Open data management plan”. The deliverables can be accessed at the following links:

- <https://zenodo.org/communities/ecipss>
- <https://www.ecipss.eu/deliverables/>

Deviations from D8.2 Dissemination Plan

None

2.7. Events & conferences

Completed activities

The ReCiPSS project partners have presented ReCiPSS project outcomes to different stakeholders at a number of industry and academic events over the duration of the project. These are listed in section 3.

Deviations from D8.2 Dissemination Plan

None

2.8. Scientific publications

Completed activities

The findings from the ReCiPSS project are published in peer-reviewed conference proceedings and journals as well as in the form of white papers and reports. ReCiPSS has followed the open access policy of Horizon 2020 by providing online access to scientific information that is free of charge to the end-user (<https://www.ecipss.eu/publications/>). All open-access publications are indexed in different databases such as ScienceDirect and Google Scholar.

Deviations from D8.2 Dissemination Plan

None

2.9. Project news and press releases

Completed activities

ReCiPSS regularly sent out press releases to inform the relevant stakeholders about the project updates and progress. All published ReCiPSS project news and press releases can be accessed at the following links

<https://www.ecipss.eu/news/>

<https://www.ecipss.eu/press-releases/>

Deviations from D8.2 Dissemination Plan

None

2.10. Open access repository

Completed activities

ReCiPSS is using Zenodo as a publicly accessible publication repository for public deliverables and written documents, as well as research data like spreadsheets or source codes. The publications from and on external providers and the research data are linked to OpenAIRE. ORCID enables the identification of authors and contributors and serves as a central source of information to enable data export and import. This eases the access of data on different platforms and supports the scientific exchange on external platforms such as ResearchGate.

Deviations from D8.2 Dissemination Plan

None

2.11. Advisory board

Completed activities

The ReCiPSS advisory board was established as a guiding mechanism for an outside view on the developments in the ReCiPSS project. The board is constituted by experts from both businesses and research with extensive experience from the economic and sustainability perspective on manufacturing systems. The advisory board consist of the following four members:

1. Sara Elisa Kettner, Project Leader at ConPolicy GmbH (Institute for Consumer Policy), <https://datenschutz-scanner.de/das-team/sara-elisa-kettner/>
2. Nick Jeffries, Insights and Analysis Team Leader at Ellen Macarthur Foundation, <https://www.linkedin.com/in/nickieffries/>
3. Nabil Nasr, Founder of the Center for Remanufacturing and Resource Recovery at the Rochester Institute of Technology, <https://www.linkedin.com/in/nabil-nasr-212a0721/>
4. Torbjörn Holm, Director of Business Development at Eurostep, a company specialized in PLM software, <https://www.linkedin.com/in/torbj%C3%B6rn-holm-5354872/>

During the course of the project, the consortium organized three advisory board meetings with members where they were informed about the project updates and progress. At the end of each advisory board meeting, a summary report was prepared for dissemination.

Deviations from D8.2 Dissemination Plan

None

2.12. Referencing and acknowledgement

Completed activities

All ReCiPSS project publications and dissemination activities have acknowledged affiliation to ReCiPSS and the funding from the European Commission the following acknowledgement statement “*This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 776577-2.*”

Deviations from D8.2 Dissemination Plan

None

3. Individual partner level communication and dissemination activities

In addition to project level communication and dissemination activities, individual partners also carried out different communication and dissemination activities.

3.1. KTH Royal Institute of Technology (KTH)

During the project, KTH carried out different types of dissemination activities, which are listed below.

No.	Activity type	Dissem. Channel type	Specify channel	Audience	Target number	Date	Comments/link
1	Web information	Public website	ReCiPSS announced at CE@KTH website.	Scientific, industry and general	10000+	Available since autumn 2018	https://www.kth.se/ce/research/research-activities
2	Presentation	Conference	World Circular Economy Forum	Academia, policy makers, industry and general.	100+	Oct 22-24 2018	http://www.recipss.eu/recipss-will-be-presented-at-the-world-circular-economy-forum-on-22-24-october-2018/
3	Other		Topic for student projects	Under Grad., Grad., and post Grad. students	50+	autumn 2018- spring 2019	Several students have written their B.Sc., M.Sc. theses on this topic
4	Other	Seminar	PhD course in Circular Industrial Systems	PhD students	30+	February - June 2019	PhD students are informed and ReCiPSS ideas have been demonstrated using a board game
5	Presentation	Conference	World Circular Economy Forum	Scientific, industry and general	200+	3-5 June 2019	ReCiPSS was presented in the EC's Stakeholders conference https://www.sitra.fi/en/projects/world-circular-economy-forum-2019/
6	Workshop	Workshop	Ellen MacArthur Foundation	Scientific, industry and general	15+	12 June 2019	High level academic dialogue on circular economy
7	Workshop	Workshop	Ellen MacArthur Foundation CE 100 Acceleration Workshops	Scientific, industry and general	200+	7-9 May 2019	Acceleration workshop to promote CMS
8	Workshop	Workshop	CE@KTH platform	Scientific	15+	10 June 2019	
9	Workshop	Workshop	XPRES	Scientific	10+	14 June 2019	XPRES pulse meeting
10	Seminar	Seminar	Rotary clubs	Industry and	30+	13 Nov 2019	ReCiPSS presented among high

			Djursholm	general			private/public officials and industrialists
11	Workshop	Workshop	1st KTH Symposium on Circular Economy for Early Career Researchers	PhD students at KTH	20+	19 November 2019	https://www.kth.se/ce/about/news/1st-kth-symposium-on-circular-economy-for-early-career-researchers-1.940524
12	Workshop	Workshop	Ellen MacArthur Foundation CE 100 Acceleration Workshops	Scientific, industry and general	200+	4-6 December 2019	Acceleration workshop to promote CMS
13	Presentation	Seminar	PhD course in Circular Industrial Systems	PhD students	20+	February - June 2020	ReCiPSS has been mentioned and proposed as an approach to CE implementation
14	Other	N/A	3 PhD students joined the project	N/A	N/A		Malvina Roci, Niloufar Salehi and Johan Arekran joined the ReCiPSS team.
15	Scientific publication	Journal	Journal of cleaner production	Academia	N/A	March 2020	https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0959652620309410
16	Seminar	Seminar	Signifikant and KTH joint webinar	Scientific, industry and general		08-apr-20	https://register.gotowebinar.com/register/377806909979611916
17	Scientific publication	Book chapter	Handbook of the Circular Economy	Academia	N/A	December 2020	https://www.elgaronline.com/view/edcoll/9781788972710/9781788972710.00036.xml
18	Scientific publication	Book chapter	Sustainable Consumption and Production, Volume II	Academia	N/A	Autumn 2020	https://link.springer.com/chapter/10.1007/978-3-030-55285-5_12
19	Presentation	Conference	Design 2020	Academia	N/A	October 2020	
20	Presentation	Conference	IS4CE2020 Circular Economy Conference, University of Exeter, Exeter, Devon, UK	Academia	N/A	July 6-7, 2020	https://www.is4ce.org/en/conference/is4ce2020/conference-proceedings
21	Presentation	Conference	The 80th Annual Meeting of the Academy of Management, Vancouver,	Academia	N/A	August 7-11, 2020	https://journals.aom.org/doi/abs/10.5465/AMBP.2020.22183abstract

			British Columbia, Canada				
22	Presentation	Seminar	XPRES at IIP, KTH	Academia	20+	27-apr-20	
23	Scientific publication	Journal	Sustainability	Academia	N/A	Jan, 2021	https://www.mdpi.com/2071-1050/13/1/344
24	Scientific publication	Journal	Journal of Cleaner Production	Academia	N/A	Feb, 2021	https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S095965262100754X
25	Presentation	Guest Lecture at MU	Lecture: Circular Manufacturing Systems: A complex but essential paradigm shift for the manufacturing industry	Students/Academia	30+	mar-21	https://www.econ.muni.cz/en/events-calendar/10905-circular-manufacturing-systems-a-complex-but-essential-paradigm-shift-for-the-manufacturing-industry
26	Presentation	Seminar	XPRES at IIP, KTH	Academia	20+	16 April, 2021	
27	Presentation	Seminar	Friday Seminar at KTH	Academia	15+	30 April 2021	
28	Scientific publication/ Presentation on ICT	Conference	Circular Materials Conference 2021	Academia/industry/policy makers	100+	April 21-22, 2021	https://www.circularmaterialsconference.se/speakers-day-1-april-21-2021/
29	Scientific publication/ Presentation on CMS	Conference	Circular Materials Conference 2021	Academia/industry/policy makers	100+	April 21-22, 2021	https://www.circularmaterialsconference.se/speakers-day-1-april-21-2021/
30	Publication	White paper	Signifikant Website	Academia/industry/policy makers	N/A	okt-20	https://www.signifikant.se/resources/#whitepapers
31	Video	Panel discussion	Online Video on youtube	Academia/industry/policy makers/general public	N/A	23 March, 2021	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=xt3RcYaFlY4
32	Stakeholder training	Workshop	Online through CirBES AB	ReCiPSS project partners	18+	15 April, 2021	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:6788806515047374848/
33	Exhibition	Virtual booth	EU Green Week	Academia/industry/policy makers/general public	N/A	June1-4, 2021	https://www.eugreenweek.eu/virtual-exhibition/kth-royal-institute-technology-h2020-project-ecipss

34	Presentation	online seminar	PhD course in CE and Industrial Systems at KTH	Academia	10+	16 June, 2021	https://kunskapsformedlingen.se/en/courses/p54-ceandindsystems/
35	Scientific publication	Master's Thesis	Sustainable Product Development and Sourcing	Academia/industry/policy makers	N/A	Started Spring 2021	N/A
36	Scientific publication	Master's Thesis	Distribution by Electric Vehicles (E-DEL)	Academia/industry/policy makers	N/A	Started Spring 2021	N/A
37	Scientific publication	Master's Thesis	KPI's for Circular Economy	Academia/industry/policy makers	N/A	Started Spring 2021	N/A
38	Scientific publication	Master's Thesis	Packaging strategy impact towards sustainable logistics operations	Academia/industry/policy makers	N/A	Started Spring 2021	N/A
39	Presentation	Seminar	Masters course in Circular Manufacturing Systems	Academia/industry/policy makers	33	Fall 2021	https://www.iip.kth.se/nyheter/the-industry-needs-experts-in-circular-manufacturing-1.1112028
40	Scientific publication	Journal	International Journal of Environmental Science and Technology	Academia/industry/policy makers	N/A	May, 2021	https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s13762-021-03388-x
41	Presentation	Seminar	2nd Advisory Board Meeting	Academia/industry/policy makers	20+	13 Oct, 2021	https://www.recipss.eu/recipss-2nd-advisory-board-meeting/
42	Workshop	Workshop	Train the trainer workshop at DTU	Academia	12+	15 Oct, 2021	N/A
43	Presentation	online Webinar	CE@KTH	Academics, students, professionals	100+	27 Oct, 2021	https://www.kth.se/ce/news/product-design-in-a-circular-economy-1.1105596
44	Presentation	Conference	HPU-IIP conference at IIP	Academia	10+	Oct, 2021	N/A
45	Scientific publication	Journal	Sustainable Production and Consumption	Academia	N/A	Jan, 2022	https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S2352550922000306?via%3Dihub

46	Exhibition	Virtual booth	EU Industry Days 2022	Academia/industry/policy makers/general public	N/A	Feb 8-11, 2022	https://euindustrydays.app.swapcard.com/event/eu-industry-days-2022/exhibitor/RXhoaWJpdG9yXzcvMzU5Ng==
47	Scientific publication	Journal	Business Strategy and the Environment	Academia	N/A	Spring 2022	https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/10.1002/bse.3108
48	Scientific publication	Journal	Resources, Conservation and Recycling	Academia	N/A	Spring 2022	https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0921344922002099?via%3Dihub
49	Scientific publication	Journal	MethodsX	Academia	N/A	Spring 2022	https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S2215016122000905
50	Presentation	seminar for CE-KTH	Lecture: The need for standardization within the Circular Economy	Students/Academia	100+	feb-22	https://www.recipss.eu/guest-lecture-on-the-need-for-standardization-within-the-circular-economy/
51	Presentation	Guest Lecture at MU	Lecture: Circular Manufacturing Systems: A complex but essential paradigm shift for the manufacturing industry	Students/Academia	30+	mar-22	ReCiPSS case studies mentioned as examples of Circular Manufacturing Systems
52	Presentation	Guest Lecture at KTH	Lecture: Advanced product design	Students/Academia	30+	mar-22	ReCiPSS case studies mentioned as examples of Circular Manufacturing Systems
53	Presentation	Guest Lecture at DTU	Towards Circular Manufacturing Systems	Students/Academia	20+	apr-22	ReCiPSS case studies mentioned as examples of Circular Manufacturing Systems
54	Presentation	Seminar IIP KTH	Designing Circular Manufacturing Systems: methods and tools for quantitative analysis	Students/Academia	30+	apr-22	ReCiPSS case studies mentioned as examples of Circular Manufacturing Systems
55	Presentation	Seminar	ReCiPSS project presented to a delegation from different German	Industry	28	maj-22	ReCiPSS case studies mentioned as examples of Circular Manufacturing Systems

			organizations				
56	Presentation	Seminar	Masters course in Circular Manufacturing Systems	Academia	100+	Fall 2022	ReCiPSS case studies mentioned as examples of Circular Manufacturing Systems
57	Presentation	Conference/Exhibition	Circular Materials Conference 2022	Academia/industry/policy makers	200+	Sep 14-15 2022	Project presentation and distribution of ReCiPSS flyers with conference participants. https://www.circularmaterialsconference.se/wp-content/uploads/2022/09/Amir-Rashid-CMC2022_1.pdf
58	Presentation	Mini course on "quantitative analysis of Circular Economy strategies" in collaboration with EFLA Consulting Engineers in Reykjavik, Iceland	CATALY(C)ST project	Industry	10+	28 Sep 2022	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:6981549968578756609
59	Scientific publication	Conference	GCSM Global Conference on Sustainable Manufacturing	Academia, policy makers, industry and general	N/A	Oct 2022	https://gcsmeu/

3.2. Delft University of Technology (TU Delft)

During the project, TU Delft carried out different types of dissemination activities, which are listed below.

No	Key activities	Dissem. channel Type	Specific channel	Audience category	Target number	Date	Comments/Link
1	Other	Other	1 post-doc to join the project	N/A	N/A	June 2018	Sonja van Dam hired
2	Other	Other	1 PhD to join the project	N/A	N/A	June 2018	Nina Boorsma hired
3	Presentation	Conference	CARE innovation conference 2018	Academics	30	November 2018	http://ci2018.care-electronics.net/
4	Scientific publication	Conference	PLATE	Academics	N/A	September 2019	https://www.recipss.eu/1698-2/

5	Scientific publication	Conference	IcoR	Academics	N/A	June 2019	http://www.remanufacturing-conference.com/ https://www.researchgate.net/publication/339747396_CIRCULAR_BUILDING_PRODUCTS_A_CASE_STUDY_OF_SOFT_BARRIERS_IN_DESIGN_FOR_REMANUFACTURING
6	Other	Other	students projects	Under grad., grad and post grad. students		February 2020	Graduation project Homie dryer in progress. Vacancy for Gorenje online. In the process of searching for a student. Uncertain of when this will start due to Corona circumstances. Graduation project C-eco on hold due to Corona circumstances.
7	Scientific publication	Journal	The Design Journal	academic	N/A	April 2020	Accessible online January 2021
8	Scientific publication	Conference	CARE innovation conference 2018	academic	N/A	November 2018	http://ci2018.care-electronics.net/ https://www.researchgate.net/publication/339747209_CAPABILITIES_REQUIRED_TO_TACKLE_BARRIERS_TO_REMANUFACTURING
9	Scientific publication	Conference	CARE innovation conference 2018	academic	N/A	November 2018	http://ci2018.care-electronics.net/ https://www.researchgate.net/publication/339747299_REMANUFACTURING_WORKSHOPS_WITH_PROFESSIONALS_TO_OVERCOME_BARRIERS_OUTCOMES_OF_TWO_EU_PROJECTS
10	Workshop	Fair	ReMaTec	Industry - Core Brokers (Automotive)	8	23 June 2019	https://www.rematec.com/news/sign-up-to-help-simplify-reverse-logistics-for-automotive-cores/
11	Workshop	Workshop	Lorch	Industry - Wholesalers (Automotive)	8	May 29 2019	
12	Presentation	Conference	European Roundtable on Sustainable Consumption and Production (ERSCP) Society	Industry, academics	200	Oct-19	https://erscp2019.eu/conny-bakker.php
13	Presentation	Other	Dutch Design Week	Industry, design consultancy,	200	Oct-19	

				general public, academics, design organisations			
14	Other	Other	Successful graduation project on design tool development, impacting the design requirements of product design at Philips and contributing to scientific literature	Product developers at multinational, product designers, academics	500+	Nov-19	https://repository.tudelft.nl/islandora/object/uuid%3A810db9a6-9718-4451-8f8f-67ad0cdccad9?collection=education
15	Scientific publication	Conference	IC4CE 2020	academic	N/A	Jul-20	
16	Scientific publication	Journal	Journal of Remanufacturing	Academic	N/A	May 2020	https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s13243-020-00090-y
17	Other	Other	rematec.com	Industry	N/A	Feb 2020	https://www.rematec.com/news/research-gets-to-the-core-of-the-issue/
18	Web information	Public website	Webpage on university website to promote the newly developed design tools	Academics, students, design professionals	400	Sep-20	
19	Workshop	Workshop	Industrial Design Engineering Master Class (IDEMC) - Design for the circular economy	Design professionals	15	January 29, 30 2020	https://www.tudelft.nl/io/studeren/ide-design-master-classes/design-for-the-circular-economy/
20	Other	Other	The Product Journey Map tool has been included in the Delft Design Guide	Industry, design consultancy, general public, academics, design organizations, design students	1000+	Feb-20	https://www.bispublishers.com/delft-design-guide-revised.html
21	Other	Other	rematec.com	Industry	N/A	Feb 2020	https://www.rematec.com/news/research-gets-to-the-core-of-the-issue/
22	Scientific publication	Conference	IC4CE 2020	academic	N/A	Jul-20	

23	Web information	Public website	Webpage on university website to promote the newly developed design tools	Academics, students, design professionals	400	Sep-20	https://www.tudelft.nl/io/onderzoek/sustainability/recipss
24	Workshop	Workshop	Bosch	Industry - OEM (Automotive)	50+	7-Oct-20	
25	scientific publication	Journal	Journal of Remanufacturing	academic	N/A	May-21	https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s13243-020-00090-y
26	Presentation	Seminar	Koninklijk Instituut Van Ingenieurs (KIVI), English: Royal Institute of Engineers	Industry, design consultancy, general public, academics, design organisations	80	New date TBD	https://www.kivi.nl/afdelingen/industrieeel-ontwerpen/activiteiten/activiteit/design-voor-een-circulaire-economie-geannuleerd-i-v-m-het-coronavirus
27	Video	Panel discussion	Through CirBES AB	Academia/industry/policy makers/general public	N/A	Mar-21	
28	Workshop	Stakeholder training	Through CirBES AB	project partners	18+	Apr-21	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:6788806515047374848/
29	News Article	ReMaTec News	DESIGN FOR REMANUFACTURING: A DESIGN MANAGEMENT PERSPECTIVE	Academia/industry/policy makers/general public	N/A	Jan-21	https://www.rematec.com/news/strategy-and-concept/design-for-remanufacturing-management-perspective/
30	Interview	other	CIRCO website	CE training network for professionals	N/A	Jan-21	https://www.circonl.nl/design-for-remanufacturing-de-vroege-ontwerpfase/
31	Webinar	online	Co-Creation To Develop Circular Product-Service System, A Case From The White Goods Sector	Academics, students, professionals	15+	16 Feb, 2021	https://www.recipss.eu/home1/events/recipss/
32	Webinar	online	Comparison of the environmental impact of a circular business model to a linear model	Academics, students, professionals	5+	12 March, 2021	https://www.recipss.eu/home1/events/recipss-webinar-on-comparison-of-the-environmental-impact-of-a-circular-business-model-to-a-linear-model/

33	Master thesis	other	University repository	Academics, students, professionals	50+	Feb 2021	http://resolver.tudelft.nl/uuid:1217e087-a4fd-49f2-b817-20cf2ba12c49
34	Master thesis	other	University repository	Academics, students, professionals	50+	July 2021	http://resolver.tudelft.nl/uuid:1217e087-a4fd-49f2-b817-20cf2ba12c49
35	Workshop	Workshop	Knorr-Bremse	Industry - OEM (Automotive)	50+	15-Jul-21	
36	Workshop	Workshop	ATAG	Industry - OEM (white goods demonstrator), consumers	50+	Fall 2021	
37	Presenation	online Webinar	CE@KTH	Academics, students, professionals	100+	27 Oct, 2021	
38	Master thesis	other	University repository (Thesis title: Product Journey map)	Academics, students, professionals	50+	feb-22	https://repository.tudelft.nl/islandora/object/uuid:5c39d067-2640-4f1a-8f09-93276d6d5fa1/datastream/OBJ/download
39	Interviews	Interview	C-ECO	Car repair workhops, end consumers (Automotive)	10+	Feb-July 2022	
40	Master thesis	other	University repository (Thesis title: 3D printed production of spare parts for the automotive industry)	Academics, students, professionals	50+	jun-22	N/A
41	Other	design method	Gorenje	Industry - OEM (White goods)	10	Fall 22	N/A
42	scientific publication	Journal paper	Journal of Remanufacturing	Academia	N/A	Feb 2022	https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s13243-021-00107-0
43	scientific publication	Journal paper	Sustainability	Academia	N/A	July 2022	https://www.mdpi.com/2071-1050/14/15/9288

3.3. Fraunhofer (FHG)

During the project, FHG carried out different types of dissemination activities, which are listed below.

No	Key activities	Dissemination	Specific	Audience	Target	Date	Comments/Link
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		channel Type	channel	category	number		
1	Presentation	Conference	World Remanufacturing Conference	Scientists and Industry	100+	19- 20 September 2018	N/A
2	Presentation	Fair	Rematec	Industry	100+	23- 25 June 2019	Tradeshaw in Amsterdam with focus to Automotive Remanufacturing industry.
3	Web information	social media	Twitter	Publicly available	100+	11-Apr-19	
4	Scientific publication	Conference	ICoR	Scientists	100+	23- 25 June 2019	International Conference on Remanufacturing
5	Other	Seminar	Include ReCiPSS project in lectures on remanufacturing at University of Bayreuth	Academy	50+	April - August 2020	N/A
6	Other	Other	1 PhD to join the project	Academy	1	May 2020	N/A
7	Other	Seminar	Include ReCiPSS project in lectures on remanufacturing at University of Bayreuth	Academy	50+	October 2020 - March 2021	N/A
8	Presentation	Conference	Bayern – Fit for Partnership "Georgia"	Industry	15	October 2020	https://bayern-fit-for-partnership.b2match.io/
9	Other	Other	Lecture about Remanufacturing and Reverse Logistics	Academy	15+	December 2020	N/A
10	Video	Panel discussion	Video recording through CirBES AB	Academia/industry/policy makers/general public	N/A	21 March, 2021	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=xt3RcYaFly4
11	Presentation	Workshop	Circular Supply Chains	Internal	14	26 March, 2021	N/A
12	Stakeholder training	Workshop	Through CirBES AB	Project partners	18+	Apr-21	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:6788806515047374848/
13	Presentation	Workshop	Circular Supply Chains	Internal	20+	07 May, 2021	N/A
14	Presentation	online seminar	PhD course in CE and	Academia	10+	16 June, 2021	https://kunskaapsformedlingen.se/en/courses/p54-

			Industrial Systems at KTH				ceandindsystems/
15	Policy Brief	Other	Other	Academia, policy makers, industry and general	N/A	Together with C-Serveees project in October 2022	https://www.eventbrite.de/e/paving-the-way-for-innovative-circular-economy-products-and-services-tickets-427049856617
16	Presentation	Webinar	webinar series: #keepthepace - game changer in automotive production	Industry	69	2022-03-10	https://www.ipa.fraunhofer.de/de/veranstaltungen-messen/veranstaltungen/2022/keepthepace.html#top1
17	Presentation	Webinar	1. Cleantech Innovation Summit »CO2-neutrale Wertschöpfung«	Academia, policy makers, industry and general	50+	Feb 2022	https://www.bayern-innovativ.de/de/veranstaltung/cleantech-innovation-summit#!programm
18	Other	Seminar	Include ReCiPSS project in lectures on remanufacturing at University of Bayreuth	Academy	50+	October 2021-March 2022	N/A
19	Scientific publication	Master Thesis	KPI's for Circular Economy	Academia/ industry/ policy makers	N/A	May 2022	N/A
20	Presentation	Other	Other	Industry	13	July 2022	N/A
21	Presentation	Other	Sommerkolloquium Produktion.Besser.machen	Academia, Industry	35	July 2022	N/A
22	Presentation	Other	DIME World Cafe	Academia, Industry	60	July 2022	N/A
23	Presentation	Other	Fraunhofer internal dissemination	Internal	50	Aug 2022	N/A
24	Scientific publication	Conference	GCSM Global Conference on Sustainable Manufacturing	Academia, policy makers, industry and general	N/A	Oct 2022	https://gcsm.eu/

3.4. Circular Economy Solutions GmbH (C-ECO)

During the project, C-ECO carried out different types of dissemination activities, which are listed below.

No	Key activities	Dissem. channel Type	Specific channel	Audience category	Target number	Date	Comments/Link
1	Presentation	Fair	Automechanika 2018	Industry	100+	11-12 September 2018	With around 4.600 exhibitors, Automechanika is the world's largest trade fair for the automotive industry with a focus on the aftermarket.
2	Presentation	Conference	Future Car	Industry, Universities, Organizations, Policy makers, etc.	50+	17 October 2018	Workshop of an innovation network "Future Car", carrying out joint research on trends and future aspects of the automotive industry. The innovation network "FutureCar" has been supported and organized by the IAO (Frauenhofer Institut für Arbeitswirtschaft und Organisation) for 9 years.
3	Presentation	Other	TU Dresden	Students, Academics, etc.	100+	1 November 2018	Kreislaufwirtschaft - Closing the loop als eigenständiges Geschäftsmodell (Circular economy - Closing the loop as an independent business model)
4	Other	Other	Press release	Publicly available	1000+	06 November 2018	Press release
5	Presentation	Fair	ReMaTec	Industry	100+	June 2019	Tradeshaw in Amsterdam with focus to Automotive Remanufacturing industry.
6	Web information	social media	Linkedin	Publicly available	100+	08 April 2019	workshop during Rematec
7	Presentation	Fair	ReMaTec	Industry	100+	23-25 June 2019	Meet global players from 74 countries active in the aftermarket linked to remanufacturing parts and/or components at ReMaTec Amsterdam 2019! https://www.rematec.com/amsterdam

8	Workshop	Fair	ReMaTec	Industry - Core Brokers (Automotive)	5	23 June 2019	Core brokers are being urged to join a workshop, which will be run by Delft University of Technology (TU Delft) at ReMaTec 2019 in Amsterdam. https://www.rematec.com/news-articles/sign-up-to-help-simplify-reverse-logistics-for-automotive-cores/#.XHjsZeaJAY.linke din
9	Report/white paper	Magazine	Industrie 4.0 Management	Industry	35000	December 2019	https://www.industrie-management.de/sites/industrie-management.de/files/pdf/klenk_Kreislaufwirtschaft-in-globalen-Wertschoepfungsnetzwerken-IM2019-6.pdf
10	Presentation	Conference	CIRP winter-meetings (Group STC O-Production systems and organizations) in Paris	Industry and academy	100+	20 February 2020	https://www.cirp.net/meetings-conferences/about-cirp-events/winter-meetings.html
11	Web information	Social media	LinkedIn	Publicly available	100+	May-20	Post for the 5th GA meeting
12	Web information	Social media	LinkedIn	Publicly available	100+	May-20	Post about the article co-authored by C-ECO's Markus Wagner about Circular Economy
13	Web information	Social media	LinkedIn	Publicly available	100+	Jun-20	Project month 24 update post on LinkedIn
14	Web information	Social media	Twitter	Publicly available	100+	Jun-20	Project update
15	Web information	Public website	C-ECO/ News	Publicly available	100+	Jun-20	Innovative through research
16	Web information	Social media	LinkedIn, Twitter	Public available	100+	Aug-20	Project update
17	Web information	Social media	LinkedIn, Twitter	Publicly available	100+	Sep-20	Post for Lorch
28	Web information	Social media	LinkedIn, Twitter	Publicly available	100+	Sep-20	Deliverables of ReCiPSS
19	Presentation	Seminar	PhD course in CE and Industrial Systems at KTH	Academia/industry/policy makers	10+	Apr-21	N/A
20	Video	Panel discussion	Through CirBES AB	Academia/industry/policy makers/gener	N/A	Mar-21	N/A

				al public			
21	Stakeholder training	Workshop	Through CirBES AB	project partners	18+	Apr-21	N/A
22	Presentation	Online-Presentation with Recording	Digital ReMaTec-fair	Industry (Remanufacturers/corebrokers),Academia	N/A	May-21	Demonstrate new business-modell opportunities basing on transferable core-options to industry; motivate feedback and further users
23	Web Information	Website News	Lorch-Website	Publicly available	100+	Mar-21	KFZ-Teile - Lorch Gruppe (lorch-gruppe.com)
24	Web Information	Website News	C-ECO Website	Publicly available	100+	Mar-21	Big milestone for ReCiPSS automotive sector » C-ECO
25	Award application		Award (bundespreis-ecodesign.de)		N/A		Application for "Bundespreis eco-design" (category "Service") which is awarded by german "Bundesumweltministerium" (Federal Ministry for the Environment, Nature Conservation and Nuclear Safety)
26	Presentation at	Guest lecture	Hochschule Heilbronn	Academia/Students	40	Oct 2021	Presentation/Lecture in front of students for supply chain management / distribution logistics
27	Presentation	Conference	Presented ReCiPSS on the circular futures Festival in Berlin and Munich	Academia/industry/policy makers/general public	N/A	Oct 2021	https://circularfutures.de/
28	Web information	LinkedIn C-ECO	Post about milestone of ReCiPSS and Lorch	Publicly available	100+	March 23th 2022	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:6912418122855514112
29	Web information	LinkedIn C-ECO	Post about ReCiPSS GA meeting	Publicly available	100+	May 20 th 2022	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:6933328886151700480
30	Web information	C-ECO website	News article on workshop for ReCiPSS platform at Automechanika	Publicly available	100+	August 12th	https://www.c-eco.com/news/more-circularity-for-the-automotive-sector/
31	Web information	LinkedIn C-ECO	6 posts on workshop for ReCiPSS	Publicly available	100+	August 15 th and 26 th , September	e.g. https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:acti

			platform at Automechanika			7 th , 12 th , 13 th and 19 th	vity:6975050289443659776 https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:6973191470035922944
32	Web information	Automechanika website	Publication about industry workshop at Automechanika for ReCiPSS platform	Publicly available	100+	Sept 2022	https://automechanika.messefrankfurt.com/frankfurt/en/programme-events/events.html#/event.detail.html/industry-workshop-core-management-as-a-service_140922-11.html?day=2022-09-14&q=industrie
33	Presentation/live-system demo	Fair	On-site Industry workshop at Automechanika Frankfurt	Remanufacturers/wholesalers/service-providers	20	Sept 2022	

3.5. Masaryk University (MU)

During the project, MU carried out different types of dissemination activities, which are listed below.

No	Key activities	Dissemination channel Type	Specific channel	Audience category	Target number	Date	Comments/Link
1	Other	Journal	<i>MUNI journal</i>	academicians, policy makers, industry and general	N/A	Autumn 2018	interview with the manager of research institute and information about the ReCiPSS project https://www.em.muni.cz/veda-a-vyzkum/11084-tridit-nestaci-musime-omezit-svoji-spotrebu
2	Other	Conference	Ifkad 2019 - session	academicians, policy makers, industry and general	250	June 2019	https://www.ifkad.org/event/ifkad-2019/
3	Scientific publication	Conference	Ifkad 2019	academicians, policy makers, industry and general	N/A	VI.19	https://www.recipss.eu/1694-2/
4	Scientific publication	Conference	Ifkad 2019 -	academician, policy makers, industry and general	N/A	Jun-19	https://www.recipss.eu/1691-2/
5	Scientific publication	Conference	Ifkad 2019 -	academician, policy makers, industry and general	N/A	Jun-19	https://www.recipss.eu/1685-2/

6	Scientific publication	Conference	Ifkad 2019 -	academician, policy makers, industry and general	N/A	Jun-19	https://www.recipss.eu/1679-2/
7	Scientific publication	Conference	Ifkad 2019 -	academician, policy makers, industry and general	N/A	Jun-19	https://www.recipss.eu/1670-2/
8	Web information	Public website	web of the Research Institute for Sustainable business at MU	academicians, policy makers, industry and general	cca 200	continuously	https://risb.econ.muni.cz/en/aktualne
9	Other	Other	Scientists' night (or Night of the scientists)	general public and academician	100 visitors + cca 800 views of the programme	27th September 2019	special whole country event hold in the university cities and town presenting science in the friendly way https://www.muni.cz/kalendar/6139-noc-vedcu-2019-setrne-k-planete-econ-muni
10	Other	Other	students' projects	master degree students	several tens	autumn 2019	23 students in 3 teams. Topics: Product lifespan, right to repair and selfrepair Customer segments for remanufactured/refurbished household products Shared laundry: students versus households
11	Other	Other	1Ph.D. students to join the project	N/A	N/A	N/A	
12	Workshop	Workshop	MJUNI 2020	children	several tens	7th February 2020	https://www.facebook.com/econmuni/photos/pcb.10157126211360910/10157126207035910/?type=3&theater
13	Scientific publication	Journal	European Journal of International Management	academicians, policy makers, industry and general	several hundreds	autumn 2020	https://www.inderscience.com/info/ingeneral/forthcoming.php?jcode=ejim
14	Other	Other	Scientists' night (or Researchers' nights)	general public and academicians	100 visitors + cca 800 views of the programme	Night - launch of the online activities - 27th November, online available autumn 2020 - summer 2021	https://www.muni.cz/en/events-calendar/9151-noc-vedcu-2020-clovek-a-robot

15	Web information	Public website	Research Institute for Sustainable Business of the Faculty of Economics and Administration MU	general public and academicians	several hundreds	autumn 2020	https://risb.econ.muni.cz/en/aktualne
16	Seminar	Seminar	3 courses, Faculty of Economics and Administration, MU	students	app. 120 students	autumn semester 2020	tasks related to washing machine as PSS and renting solved during the seminars within the courses: Corporate Social Responsibility; Operations Management and Introduction to the Informatics
17	Seminar	Seminar	2 courses, Faculty of Management and Economics, University of Tomsa Bata, Zlín, Czechia	students	app. 80 students	autumn semester 2020	tasks related to washing machine as PSS and renting in the context of the ethical issues solved during the seminars within the courses: Business ethics and Managerial ethics
18	Other	Other	Lecture about remanufacturing (within the course Logistics and Supply Chain Management)	Academy	15+	December 2020	Online Guest Lecture by FHG
19	Other	Other	Lecture about simulation (within the course Corporate Management Systems)	Academy	30+	N/A	Online Guest Lecture by KTH
20	Other	Other	Lecture about barriers and fears of pay-per-use model (within the course Consumer behavior)	Academy	N/A	N/A	Online Guest Lecture by MU
21	Video	Panel discussion	Through CirBES AB	Academician/industry/policy makers/general public	N/A	Mar-21	Available online
22	Presentation	Seminar	PhD course in CE and Industrial Systems at KTH	Students	15+	16 June, 2021	https://www.kth.se/ce/news/recipss-day-as-part-of-the-phd-course-in-circular-economy-and-industrial-systems-1.1080991

23	Other	Other	whole semester course, Faculty of Economic and Administration, Masaryk University	students	15	September 2021 - December 2021	students work on different countries analysis for the identification of market potential for pay per wash service business
24	Other	Other	lecture (Faculty of Economics and Administration, Masaryk University)	students	48	October 2021	lecture on Product Service Systems, pay per use services and cloud for the product flows within the ReCiPSS project
25	Other	Other	Scientists' night (or Researchers' nights)	general public and academicians	several hundreds	officially 24th September 2021, but still available online	podcast titled "We do not have time anymore" (in Czech "Už nemáme čas") presenting ReCiPSS project in the context of sustainable development and Green Deal https://www.nocvedcu.cz/udalost/3814-uz-nemame-cas
26	Presentation	Workshop	workshop of the Department of Economy (FEA MU) and guests	academicians	38	September 2021	presentation of ReCiPSS project and discussion
27	Other	Seminar	2 seminars, Faculty of Management and Economics, Tomas Bata University in Zlín	students	30+	April 2022	consumer behavior and pay per wash - students will work on their perception and barriers in relation to pay per wash
28	Other	Other	Master degree thesis. University repository (Thesis title: Evaluation of the circular business mode)	students and general public	NA	June 2022	https://is.muni.cz/auth/th/x5gcn/
29	Presentation	Workshop	workshop of The Department of Economy (FEA MU) and guests	academicians	40	September 2022	presentation of the newest outcomes of the project and discussion
30	Seminar	Seminar	seminars of Business ethics course at University of	students	120	Planned for October 2022	working on the topic of ethical issues in PPU, PSS and remanufacturing

			Tomas Bata in Zlin, Faculty of Management and Economics				
31	Presentation	Other	Lecture of Operations Management course at Masaryk University, Faculty of Economics and Administration (FEA)	students	60	Planned October 2022	lecture on PSS - focused on demonstrators' cases
32	Seminar	Seminar	seminar of Corporate Social Responsibility course at Masaryk University, Faculty of Economics and Administration (FEA)	students	70	Planned during fall 2022	working on the topic of responsibility in PPU, PSS and remanufacturing

3.6. Homie Group B.V. (HOM)

During the project, HOM carried out different types of dissemination activities, which are listed below.

No	Key activities	Dissem. channel Type	Specific channel	Audience category	Target number	Planned Time	Comments/Link
1	Presentation	Conference	New Retail Champion Awards	general public	200+	Q4 2018	
2	Presentation	Seminar	Aalborg University Copenhagen campus	academics	35	Q4 2018	Mentioning HOMIE and Recipps project during presentation
3	Presentation	Conference	Kennismakers - Belgian scientific funding board - 90 year anniversary event	Academician, policy makers, industry and general.	1300+	Q4 2018	Mentioning HOMIE and Recipps project during keynote presentation
4	Presentation	Seminar	Sustainable Finance event The Green Village	general public	200+	Q1 2019	

5	Newsletter	Social media	Homie customer newsletter & website	general public	1000+	Q2 2019	Test new UI design with Homie test customers
6	Workshop	Workshop	The Green Village Test Lab	academics	10+	Q2 2019	Test new UI design with Homie test customers
7	Presentation	Conference	NBS	academics	500	Q2 2019 (annual conference)	Mentioning HOMIE and Recipps project during keynote presentation
8	presentation	seminar	UC Berkeley USA, Open Innovation Seminars (Henry Chesbrough)	academics	50+	Q2 2019	Mentioning HOMIE and Recipps project during presentation
9	Presentation	Conference	Academy of Management	Academician, policy makers, industry and general.	15,000+	Q3 2019 (annual conference)	Mentioning HOMIE and ReCiPSS project during presentation
10	Demonstration	Fair	The Green Village Test Lab	general public	N/A	2020	Demonstrate new WM in public test setting
11	Demonstration	Fair	Dutch Design Week	Academician, policy makers, industry and general.	N/A	Q3 2020	

3.7. PDS Vision Oy (PDS)

During the project, PDS carried out different types of dissemination activities, which are listed below.

No	Key activities	Dissem. channel Type	Specific channel	Audience category	Target number	Date	Comments/Link
1	Seminar	Seminar	PDS Forum	General public	50	Q2 - 2019	Circular economy as a topic in our yearly forum
2	Demonstration	Fair	Alihankinta 2019	General public	300	Sep - 2019	Goal is to be able to demonstrate concept in the trade show
3	Presentation	Conference	Manufacturing Performance Days 2019	Partners	150	May-19	Small seminar held in Stuttgart at the time of PTC Forum Europe
4	Blog post	pdsvision.com	pdsvision.com	Public blog post		Jun-20	https://www.pdsvision.com/blog/the-need-of-digital-twins-to-support-circular-economy/
5	Demonstration	Fair	Alihankinta 2020	General Public	300	Sep-20	

6	EU Green Week	on-line EU event	virtual conference	Public event		May-21	https://register.gotowebinar.com/recording/4242817874598897409
7	Demonstration	Internal PDSVISION event	PDSCONFERENCE	PDSVISION Global	200	Aug-21	
8	Demonstration	Fair	Alihankinta 2021	General Public	300	Sep-21	

3.8. Signifikant Svenska AB (SIG)

During the project, SIG carried out different types of dissemination activities, which are listed below.

No	Key activities	Dissem. channel Type	Specific channel	Audience category	Target number	Date	Comments/Link
1	Web information	Public website	company's web-site	general public		2019	https://www.signifikant.se/research-development%e2%80%8b/
2	Report/white paper	Public website	LinkedIn and company's web site	general public	215	Nov-19	https://www.signifikant.se/resources/#whitepapers
3	Report/white paper	Public website	LinkedIn and company's web site	general public		Nov-19	https://www.signifikant.se/resources/#whitepapers
4	Other	Public website	Company's website	general public		Nov-19	https://www.signifikant.se/make-and-dispose-or-make-and-reuse-the-future-is-circular-2/
5	Web information	Public website	LinkedIn	general public	110	Nov-19	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:6605509212766384128
6	Web information	Public website	LinkedIn	general public	120	Dec-19	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:6630796915544072192
7	Web information	Public website	GoToWebinar, Website and LinkedIn	general public	1800	Mar-20	https://attendee.gotowebinar.com/recording/7861010465494476040 ; https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:6644188699510870016 ; https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:6646336543281807360
8	Other	Public website	Emailers, Company Website	general public	400	2 April 2020	Other

9	Seminar	Seminar	GoToWebinar, Website and LinkedIn, Emailers	general public	N/A	8 April 2020	https://attendee.gotowebinar.com/register/3777806909979611916
10	Publication	White paper	Signifikant Website	Academician/industry/policy makers	N/A	Oct-20	Published online
11	Video	Panel discussion	Through CirBES AB	Academician/industry/policy makers/general public	N/A	Mar-21	Available online

3.9. CirBES AB (CIR)

During the project, CIR carried out different types of dissemination activities, which are listed below.

No	Key activities	Dissem. channel Type	Specific channel	Audience category	Target number	Date	Comments/Link
1	Workshop	Workshop	KTH PhD course	Students	30	07 February 2019	-
2	Workshop	Workshop	Leksaksbiblioteket	General public	10+	3 April 2019	
3	Presentation	Public seminar	Seminar on circular economy from theory to implementation	Industry	10+	27 May 2019	https://www.eventbrite.com/e/circular-economy-from-theory-to-implementation-registration-60876667752
4	Presentation	Seminar	Djursholm Svitiod Rotaryklubb	Entrepreneurs	30+	12 June 2019	
5	Workshop	Workshop	KTH PhD course	Students	20	06/02/2020	CirBES board game on Circular Manufacturing Systems https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:6632579237482164225
6	Scientific publication	Book chapter: Towards Circular Economy: Enhanced Decision-Making in Circular Manufacturing Systems	Palgrave Macmillan Publisher	Academics	389 downloads/ not specified	11/8/2020	https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-55285-5_12

7	Video	Panel discussion on the role of simulation in decision making for circular manufacturing systems	Online/video recording	Academician/industry/policy makers/general public	226 views/ not specified	Mar-21	https://youtu.be/xt3RcYaFly4?t=251
8	Stakeholder training	Workshop format developed by CirBES on circular supply chains	Online	Project partners	18+	Apr-21	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:6788806515047374848
9	Other	Social media	LinkedIn	General public	N/A	Regular update	Ongoing dissemination activity
10	Webinar	Webinar on simulation techniques	Online/video recording	Academician/industry/policy makers/general public	29 views/ not specified	sep-21	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=ACAO4N7ZiKE
11	Webinar	Webinar on circular supply chains in the automotive industry	Online/video recording	Academician/industry/policy makers/general public	N/A	nov-21	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=6hQSVnLtCel
12	Webinar	Webinar on circular supply chains in the Whitegoods industry	Online/video recording	Academician/industry/policy makers/general public	N/A	jan-22	https://youtu.be/wX0OfW2SRQI
13	Presentation	Seminar (online)	Msc course in Logistics and Supply Chain at Masaryk University	Academician	15+	maj-22	
14	Scientific publication	Conference	Global Conference on Sustainable Manufacturing (GCSM) in Berlin, Germany	Academician, policy makers, industry and general	N/A	Summer 2022	https://gcsm.eu/
15	Workshop	Workshop with a Board Game developed by CirBES on circular economy	Bosch/ CECO	Industry - OEM (Automotive)	10	01-jun-22	

16	Scientific publication	Journal	Journal of Business Strategy and Environment	Academics	N/A	Sep-2022	
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3.10. Software Imagination & Vision (SIM)

During the project, SIM carried out different types of dissemination activities, which are listed below.

No	Key activities	Dissem. channel Type	Specific channel	Audience category	Target number	Date	Comments/Link
1	Publish project updates	website	company's web-site	general public	100		http://www.siveco.ro/en/about-siveco-romania/press/press-releases/siveco-steps-along-revolution-circular-economy-no-more
2	Distribute electronic brochure periodically	social media	project's social media account/company's social media account	similar projects/eu projects(includic academic and industry partner)	N/A	yearly	
3	Publish project updates	website	company's web-site	general public(includic eu projects, similar projects,..)	N/A	2020	after each consortium meeting
4	Publish project updates	website	company's web-site	general public(includic eu projects, similar projects,..)	N/A	2021	after each consortium meeting
5	Announcement of SIMAVI entering the project on Twitter	Social Media	Linkedin	general public(includic eu projects, similar projects,..)	N/A	Oct-20	
6	Press Communicate released	website	company's web-site	general public(includic eu projects, similar projects,..)	N/A	Apr-21	https://www.simavi.ro/en/node/66
7	Press Communicate released	Social Media	Twitter	general public(includic eu projects, similar projects,..)	N/A	Apr-21	https://twitter.com/simavromania/status/1387369149849083909
8	Press Communicate released	Social Media	Facebook	general public(includic eu projects, similar projects,..)	N/A	Apr-21	https://www.facebook.com/SIMAVI.RO/posts/298600918426563

9	Press Communicate released	Social Media	Linkedin	general public(includi c eu projects, similar projects,..)	N/A	Apr-21	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:6793137094387666945
10	News article	Online website	Ziare.com	general public(includi c eu projects, similar projects,..)	N/A	Apr-21	https://ziare.com/afaceri/stiri-afaceri/recipss-sisteme-circulare-de-servicii-si-produse-eficiente-din-punct-de-vedere-al-resurselor-1675941
11	News article	Online website	Agerpres.ro	general public(includi c eu projects, similar projects,..)	N/A	Apr-21	https://www.agerpres.ro/ots/2021/04/28/recipss-sisteme-circulare-de-servicii-si-produse-eficiente-din-punct-de-vedere-al-resurselor--643765
12	Workshop	workshop	Polytechnic University of Bucharest	Students	20+	sep-21	

3.11. Gorenje Gospodinjski Aparati D.D. (GOR)

During the project, GOR carried out different types of dissemination activities, which are listed below.

No	Key activities	Dissem. channel Type	Specific channel	Audience category	Target number	Date	Comments/Link
1	Presentation	Conference	World Circular Economy Forum	Academician, policy makers, industry and general.	100+	22-24 October 2018	Mr. Ales Mihelic participated the World Circular Economy Forum
2	Report/white paper	Journal		All	100+	June 2018	
3	Report/white paper	Public website		All	1000+	October 2018	https://static14.gorenje.com/files/default/corporate/Professional-contributions/2018/GIB_04-06_2018-RECIPSS.pdf
4	Presentation	Social media	LinkedIn	All	100+	Q2/2019	Gorenje shared ReCiPSS publications on LinkedIn
5	Presentation	Conference	United Nations Industrial Development Organisation (UNIDO)	General	100+	1 April 2019	Mr. Ales Mihelic participated the conference organized by United Nations Industrial Development Organisation (UNIDO)
6	Demonstration	Other	Gospodarska zbornica	General	1000+	1 November	Prototype of WM for ReCiPSS presented on

			Slovenije			2018	Gospodarska zbornica Slovenije
7	Demonstration	Other	Ministry of the environmental and spatial planning, Slovenia	General	1000+	2 December 2018	Prototype of WM for ReCiPSS presented on Ministry of the environmental and spatial planning, Slovenia
8	Web information	Other	Gorenje Intranet	Internal, English	1000+	1 April 2019	Gorenje was discussed at the United Nations Organization for Industrial Development UNIDO https://portal.gorenje.si/SitePages/Obvestila/Novice.aspx
9	Web information	Other	Gorenje Intranet	Internal, Slovenian	1000+	1 April 2019	At the United Nations Industrial Development Organisation (UNIDO) people talked of Gorenje
10	Newsletter	Magazine	GIB Gorenje Informacijski bilten	Internal weekly information bilten	1000+	1 April 2019	
11	Presentation	Conference	ZEOS conference, CHANGING PEOPLE'S WASTE MANAGEMENT HABITS	Professional conference 2019	50+	28th-29th November 2019	http://e-odpadki.zeos.si/en/activities/conference-2019.html
12	Scientific publication	Other	Ecology day	All participants	100+	6/4/2019	Dr. Aleš Mihelič is one of the speakers on the event
13	Presentation	Other	Interview - September 26, 2018 RTV SLO1 Studio at 17h. - Innovators	All, Slovenia	1000+	26th of September 2018	Dr. Ales Mihelic participated in radio interview
14	Workshop	Workshop	ReCiPSS - Web store	Professionals	20+		Several divisions involved. Several workshops completed. Results will be implemented in ReCiPSS White goods demonstrators
15	Workshop	Workshop	ReCiPSS - Business Process proposal	Internal	10+	30th of September 2020	Several divisions involved. Results will be implemented in ReCiPSS white goods demonstrators
16	Workshop	Workshop	ReCiPSS backend processes and integration	Internal	10+	8th of October 2020	Several divisions involved. Results will be implemented in ReCiPSS white goods

			into current IT system				demonstrators.
17	Workshop	Workshop	ReCiPSS web store design	Profesionals	20+	15th of October 2020	Several divisions involved. Results will be implemented in ReCiPSS white goods demonstrators.
18	Workshop	Workshop	ReCiPSS payment options workshop	Internal	10+	September/October 2020	Several divisions involved. Several workshops completed. Results will be implemented in ReCiPSS white goods demonstrators
19	Workshop	Workshop	ReCiPSS professional user stories	Internal	10+	September/October 2020	Several divisions involved. Several workshops completed. Results will be implemented in ReCiPSS white goods demonstrators
20	Workshop	Workshop	ReCiPSS home user - user stories	Internal	10+	September/October 2020	Several divisions involved. Several workshops completed. Results will be implemented in ReCiPSS white goods demonstrators
21	Web information	Public website	Information on demonstrator start up	NL, SLO	500	May 2020	Presentation of ReCiPSS project and PPU business model
22	Web information	Public website	Information on demonstrator start up	DK, NL, SLO	500	Dec-20	Presentation of ReCiPSS project and PPU business model
23	Web information	Social media	LinkedIn	NL, SLO	500	May 2020	Presentation of ReCiPSS project and PPU business model
24	Web information	Social media	LinkedIn	DK, NL, SLO	500	Dec-20	Presentation of ReCiPSS project and PPU business model
25	Presentation	Seminar	PhD course in CE and Industrial Systems at KTH	Academician/industry/policy makers	10+	Apr-21	
26	Video	Panel discussion	Through CirBES AB	Academician/industry/policy makers/general public	N/A	Mar-21	
27	Workshop	Stakeholder training	Through CirBES AB	project partners	18+	Apr-21	
28	Demonstration	Other	Begining of large scale	NL, SLO	200	may-dec 2021	Delivery of appliances to the market

			demonstrator				
29	Demonstration	Other	Beginning of large scale demonstrator	DK, SE	220	may-dec 2021	Delivery of first appliances to the market
30	Presentation	Conference	Presentation of the ReCiPSS project on Hisense Europe Tech conference	Internal/International	100+	June 2022	Presentation of ReCiPSS project and PPU business model

3.12. STRIEBIG LOGISTIQUE (STR)

During the project, STR carried out different types of dissemination activities, which are listed below.

No	Key activities	Dissem. channel Type	Specific channel	Audience category	Target number	Date	Comments/Link
1	Presentation	Fair	Fair: Messe SITL Paris	Logistics, automotive with Road transport, Trade /distribution	The SITL show attracted a total of 30,750 visitors	May 2019	Explain the process and benefits of the circular economy and the market economy
2	Presentation	Fair	Fair: Messe Munich 2019	Transport-Logistics	The SITL show attracted a total of 63 000 visitors	June 2019	Explain the process and benefits of the circular economy and the market economy
3	Presentation	Fair	SIL Messe Barcelonne-Transport-Logistics	Transport-Logistics	The SIL Barcelona attracted a total of 11.000 visitors	June 2019	Explain the process and benefits of the circular economy and the market economy

3.13. ROBERT BOSCH GMBH (BOSCH)

During the project, BOSCH carried out different types of dissemination activities, which are listed below.

No	Key activities	Dissem. channel Type	Specific channel	Audience category	Target number	Date	Comments/Link
1	Brochures	Fair		all	N/A	June 2019	
2	Web information	Social media	LinkedIn	Publicly available	100+	May-20	Link to ReCiPSS Webpage shared
3	Presentation	Other	Bosch Internal	Reman. specialists/ engineers	25	June 2020	Presentation of ReCiPSS project and detailed selection

							<p>results of the Common Rail Injector 2-18 at Bosch. Evaluated data/results to be used as valuable base for the reman. platform development of the Common Rail Injector 2-18</p>
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4. Planned dissemination activities

As the ReCiPSS project is continuing there are many dissemination activities that the consortium partners have planned for the coming months and after the completion of the project. Some of the planned dissemination activities are mentioned below.

- The White Goods demonstrator Gorenje is planning to organise an industry workshop for the white goods sector to disseminate the developments and innovations to relevant stakeholders. The expected date for the workshop is at the end of November 2022. There are ongoing negotiations to make it part of the [Nordic Circular Summit](#) on 22-24 Nov 2022 in Stockholm, Sweden.
- ReCiPSS coordinator KTH is planning to present ReCiPSS case studies at the [Nordic Circular Summit](#) on 22-24 Nov 2022 in Stockholm, Sweden. The case studies will be presented as part of the side session on “Circular Tools – Sustaining Natural Value” on 24 Nov 2022.
- ReCiPSS coordinator KTH is planning to organize ReCiPSS Day on Nov 15/16 where all partners and relevant stakeholders will be invited. The partners will prepare posters and presentations on ReCiPSS developments and innovations.
- ReCiPSS ICT partners SIMAVI, SIGNIFIKANT and PDS Vision are planning to organize an online workshop on “IT solutions for circular economy” in Nov 2022. The relevant stakeholders from the industry will be invited.
- ReCiPSS academic partners, KTH, TU Delft, MU and FHG are planning to continue publishing in scientific journals based on ReCiPSS results.
- Gorenje is planning to continue collecting user feedback from test cases as input for future development of their pay-per-use business model
- ReCiPSS ICT partner SIGNIFIKANT plans to continue further development of their ICT solution to support the implementation of circular economy by focusing on product use and value recovery activities.
- ReCiPSS partners MU and KTH will continue further research and development on Circular Manufacturing Systems by focusing on developing integrated digital solutions for digitalising value management.
- ReCiPSS partner TU Delft plans to use ReCiPSS tools (disassembly map, product journey map) in new graduation projects with the industry as there is great interest from the industry in these tools. Already, the Product Journey Map tool is made part of a book and will be taught to bachelor students at TUD (approx. 300 students every year). The book is translated into Chinese and is sold worldwide, which will help dissemination of the Product Journey Map method.

5. Conclusion

This document lists the communication and dissemination activities carried out during the ReCiPSS project based on the dissemination plan devised at the start of the project. It lists both project and individual partner-level dissemination activities. At the project level, a major focus has been on developing a graphic identity for the project that includes the ReCiPSS logo and standardized materials such as templates and flyers. The ReCiPSS website provides detailed information about the ReCiPSS case studies and the developments and innovations made during the project. It also includes links to public deliverables and scientific publications. Currently, there are 21 public deliverables and 25 open-access scientific publications that can be accessed through the ReCiPSS website. ReCiPSS project is also active on social media that include a LinkedIn page, Twitter handle and a ReCiPSS project community on ResearchGate. At the individual partner level, ReCiPSS results have been presented at several events that include seminars, conferences and workshops. The project consortium has plans to continue disseminating ReCiPSS results even after the completion of the project through scientific publications, industry workshops and seminars. Lastly, the ReCiPSS results will be used as input for other research and development projects such as a newly funded Horizon Europe project *DiCiM: Digitalised Value Management for Unlocking the potential of the Circular Manufacturing Systems with integrated digital solutions*.

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